

OCCURRENCE OF PSORALEN IN *PHEBALIUM* *ARGENTEUM*, SMITH.

BY P. K. BOSE AND H. H. FINLAYSON.

In course of an examination of the essential oil of the Australian plant, *Phebalium argenteum* (N. O. Rutaceae) one of us isolated a colourless crystalline substance, m.p. 165° (Finlayson, *Trans. Roy. Soc.*, South Australia, 1928, 52, 235). This was supposed to be a coumarin derivative on account of its characteristic odour. Further examination could not be undertaken owing to the extremely poor yield of the material. This compound has now been further purified by sublimation at $120-30^{\circ}/0.05$ mm. and subsequent crystallisation from methyl alcohol, when it formed almost transparent prismatic needles, m.p. $166-67^{\circ}$. It behaves like a lactone and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a pale greenish yellow colour. We thought that the compound might be identical with psoralen, which had been isolated from the seeds of *Psoralea corylifolia* (Jois, Manjunath and Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 41), and from the leaves of *Ficus Carica* L. (Okahara, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1936, 11, 389),

Through the kindness of Dr. B. L. Manjunath, to whom our best thanks are due, we obtained a specimen of psoralen which after repeated sublimations in high vacuum and crystallisations melted at $166-67^{\circ}$. The properties of the two compounds were found to be identical and a mixture of the two also melted at $166-67^{\circ}$. The coumarin isolated from *P. argenteum* is thus proved to be psoralen.

UNIVERSITIES OF CALCUTTA
AND ADELAIDE.

Received August 17, 1938.
